

T.H.N. Nguyen,

PhD student

D.T. Agheorghiesei

Professor

Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi, Romania

OPTIMIZING THE STATISTICAL DISTRIBUTION OF HEALTHCARE RESOURCES IN EUROPE

Abstract. Currently, the European healthcare system faces significant challenges in allocating healthcare resources and costs due to considerable differences in organizational structure and healthcare capacity among member states. This paper analyzes statistical optimization methods for efficient healthcare resource allocation using descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and optimization models. The research results show that statistical optimization methods help improve healthcare productivity and enhance equity in access to healthcare. Furthermore, these findings assist healthcare managers in designing strategies and policies for system development.

Keywords: healthcare resources, optimizing statistical, healthcare systems, Europe.

Introduction. The European healthcare system currently faces numerous challenges related to increasing migration, limited infrastructure, and financial constraints. This leads to inequality in access to healthcare and reduced healthcare productivity among member states (WHO). To improve healthcare productivity, healthcare facilities must ensure efficient allocation of healthcare resources. Optimization statistical methods help healthcare managers identify the causes of disparities among member states and design appropriate models for allocating healthcare personnel. This study analyzes resource allocation and proposes statistical optimization methods for efficient healthcare resource allocation based on available data.

Literature review. Many studies on the topic of health economics and public administration emphasize the importance of efficient resource allocation to improve the productivity of the health care system (Mihaylova et. al. 2011). Key statistical indicators, including the number of doctors per 1000 population, the number of hospital beds per capita, and health care expenditure, are widely used to assess medical capacity (Eurostat; OECD, 2025). Regression analysis and optimization models are frequently employed to identify the relationship between health resources and health system productivity. Reliable data sources including Eurostat, the World Health Organization and the OECD, provide data that support analysis and comparison of health statistics across members, and also assist health managers in improving health policies. However, as significant differences in access to healthcare persist across Europe, there is a need for improved analytical models that integrate statistical methods with optimization techniques.

Methodology: This study employs a combination of descriptive statistical analysis, regression modeling, and empirical data optimization. Source data were obtained from Eurostat and available literature, including indicators of total doctor and hospital bed numbers, healthcare spending, and population. A multivariate linear regression model was applied to assess the relationship between resources and health productivity. The dependent variable is average life expectancy, and explanatory variables include resources, infrastructure, and healthcare financing. These variables assess the capacity of resources and health productivity among the EU.

Table 1. Healthcare resources in selected European countries

Country	Doctors	Beds	Expenditure	Age 65+	Life Expectancy
Belgium	4.0	5.4	6441	14.2	76.6
Bulgaria	3.0	8.6	7499	18.4	71.3
Czechia	4.6	6.4	2675	16.1	73.5
Denmark	2.7	2.3	3581	15.3	75.5
Germany	39.3	7.7	4916	15.0	74.2
Ireland	2.0	2.9	3353	11.6	78.8
Spain	21.2	2.9	1382	14.2	78.4
France	26.6	5.4	3251	15.2	75.5
Italy	31.6	3.0	1792	16.4	79.0
Lithuania	1.3	5.5	5401	14.4	70.4
Hungary	3.5	6.5	1260	16.0	71.3
Netherlands	7.0	2.3	1050	15.3	77.4
Austria	5.0	6.6	5278	13.7	76.0
Poland	14.1	6.3	5368	15.6	72.0
Romania	7.1	7.3	1852	15.3	72.3
Slovenia	7.4	4.0	5948	15.8	75.1
Finland	1.6	2.8	2857	17.4	77.4
Switzerland	4.0	4.4	9668	13.7	81.0

Source: Eurostat. *Healthcare Resource Statistics in Europe (2023)*.

Table 2. Model Summary

Model	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.673	0.573	2.0002

Table 3. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
1	Regression	107.380	4	26.845	6.695
	Residual	52.125	13	4.010	
	Total	159.505	17		

Table 4. Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized B	Coefficient	Coefficients Std. Error	t	sig.
Constant	85.097	85.097	5.137	16.567	0.000
Doctors	0.075	0.075	0.044	1.716	0.110
Beds	-1.183	-1.184	0.273	-4.336	0.001
Health expenditure	0.000	0.0004	0.000	1.768	0.101
Age 65+	-0.411	-0.411	0.339	-1.212	0.247

Source: *Own processing*

Regression Model

The estimated regression equation can be performed for each country:

$$LE = 85.097 + 0.075(D) - 1.184(B) + 0.0004(HE) - 0.411(A).$$

Where: LE = Life expectancy (years); D = Doctors/1000 inhabitants; B = Hospital beds/1000 inhabitants; HE = Healthcare expenditure (€); A = Population aged 65+ (%)

The empirical regression model shows that health resources significantly influence life expectancy in member countries. The results indicate that the number of doctors and health investment positively affect health productivity, while the number of hospital beds and population distribution negatively affect life expectancy.

Results. Preliminary statistical observations reveal significant disparities in healthcare capacity and productivity among European countries. Countries with higher per capita healthcare spending and more abundant healthcare human resources generally have better productivity and longer life expectancy. Regression analysis shows that physician availability and healthcare spending are the most important predictors of healthcare system performance. The rational allocation of healthcare resources across regions to enhance healthcare productivity requires healthcare systems to employ appropriate statistical optimization models. Linear regression model can be used to determine the optimal allocation of healthcare resources, but it must consider healthcare capacity among different areas. This model assists managers in developing strategies to improve access to healthcare services and forecast alternative resource allocation options when needed, while minimizing regional inequalities.

Conclusion: This paper analyzed the allocation of healthcare resources and differences in healthcare capacity among European Member States. These findings can assist managers in developing appropriate workforce allocation or replacement strategies and improving healthcare productivity. Future research should incorporate more advanced analytical methods to improve predictive capabilities in healthcare resource and cost management.

References

1. Eurostat. *Healthcare Resource Statistics in Europe*.

2. Ingole & Piyush. (2024). Optimizing Resource Allocation in Hospitals Using Predictive Analytics and Information Systems. *Journal of Information Systems Engineering and Management*. 10. 400-415. 10.52783/jisem.v10i1s.224.

3. Jin, B., et al. (2025). Optimizing health promotion resource allocation and health facility spatial layout to match supply and demand: A fairness–Efficiency synergy approach, *Habitat International*, Volume 165, 2025, 103561, ISSN 0197-3975, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2025.103561>.

4. Mihaylova, B., et al. (2011). Review of statistical methods for analysing healthcare resources and costs. *Health economics*, 20(8), 897–916. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hec.1653>

5. OECD (2025). *Health at a Glance 2025. OECD Indicators*.

6. Russo. S., et al. (2025). Developing a predictive model for resource allocation in healthcare: A case study from an Italian Hospital, *SSM - Health Systems*, Volume 5, 2025, 100085, ISSN 2949-8562, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmhs.2025.100085>.

7. World Health Organization (WHO). *European health report 2024: keeping health high on the agenda*.

I. Dorogaia,

Phd, associate professor

O. Caminschi

PhD student

Academy of Economic Studies of Moldova

DEVELOPING A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY THROUGH THE USE OF SMART TECHNOLOGIES

The topic of this research is highly relevant in the context of the global transformations of the past decade. The rapid spread of SMART technologies — from artificial intelligence systems and the Internet of Things to platform-based resource management solutions — is fundamentally changing the operating logic of both individual enterprises and national economies as a whole. At the same time, challenges related to environmental pressure, energy consumption, and the need to transition to sustainable development models are intensifying, forcing entrepreneurs, government officials, and public figures to reconsider conventional approaches to economic activity.